

ARTICLE INFO

©2026 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJASTR-
69D78B9BDEF6E

Published: 2026-05-04

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20021026>

Page No: 2/1-2/16

**Evaluation of Remote Sensing Precipitation
Estimates: A Case Study of Jalingo, Taraba State,
Northeast Nigeria**

Emerson, K.U.^{1*}, Okereke, N.A.A.², Okorafor, O.O.², and Asonye, G.U.².

¹Department of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering, Federal University
Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering, Federal University of
Technology, Owerri, Nigeria

Abstract- Reliable rainfall information is essential for climate monitoring, hydrological modeling, and water resources management, particularly in data-scarce regions such as Northeast Nigeria. This study evaluated the performance of five satellite-based remote sensing precipitation products—CHIRPS, TAMSAT, PERSIANN, PERSIANN-CCS, and PERSIANN-PDIR NOW—against gauge observations from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMET) over Jalingo, Northeast Nigeria, for the period 2002–2024. Monthly rainfall data were analyzed to examine total rainfall climatology, seasonal variability, and interannual fluctuations. Quantitative assessment of satellite products was carried out using Mean Bias Error (MBE), Relative Mean Bias Error (rMBE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Pearson correlation coefficient (r), and Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE). The results show that all satellite products reproduced the unimodal rainfall regime of Jalingo, with peak rainfall occurring between July and September. CHIRPS exhibited the best overall performance, characterized by very low bias ($MBE \approx -11.8$ mm; $rMBE \approx -0.10$), the lowest RMSE (≈ 19.1 mm), an exceptionally high correlation with NiMET observations ($r \approx 0.99$), and the highest KGE (≈ 0.90). TAMSAT and PERSIANN-PDIR NOW also showed strong correlations ($r \approx 0.99$) but displayed moderate negative biases and lower KGE values (≈ 0.56), indicating systematic underestimation of rainfall amounts. In contrast, PERSIANN and PERSIANN-CCS significantly overestimated rainfall, with higher positive biases, larger RMSE, weaker correlations (particularly for PERSIANN-CCS), and lower KGE values (≈ 0.49 and 0.29 , respectively). A preliminary analysis shows that the wettest years were 2019 and 2021 respectively, where the annual rainfall was $> 65\%$ above the long-term mean; whereas the driest years were 2006 and 2024 respectively, which showed 20% less rainfall compared to the long-term mean. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of local validation of satellite rainfall products and confirm that CHIRPS is the most reliable dataset for long-term rainfall analysis and hydrological applications in Jalingo, Northeast Nigeria.

Keywords: CHIRPS, Jalingo, Kling–Gupta Efficiency, NiMET, PERSIANN, rainfall climatology, Remote Sensing

Corresponding Author: Emerson, K.U. (kemerson@hotmail.co.uk)

Cite This Paper: Emerson, K.U.^{*}, Okereke, N.A.A., Okorafor, O.O. and Asonye, G.U. (2026). "Evaluation of Satellite Precipitation Estimates: A Case Study of Jalingo, Taraba State, Northeast Nigeria". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)*, vol. 16, Issue 3, 2026, pp. 2/1-2/16. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20021026>

1. Introduction

Accurate spatio-temporal measurement of precipitation is fundamental for assessing both rainfall deficits and surpluses [1]. Such measurements enable effective monitoring of precipitation dynamics and their impacts on hydro-ecological systems and water resources management [2], [3]. At the global scale, reliable precipitation information is critical for sustainable socio-economic development, particularly in regions with low rainfall regimes, and in many developing countries where rainfall underpins key socio-economic activities, especially agriculture [4], [5].

Traditionally, ground-based rain gauge stations have been regarded as the most reliable source of precipitation data for hydrological applications [6]. However, in many developing regions and countries, rain gauge networks are often sparse and unevenly distributed [7], [8]. This limitation is largely attributed to inadequate infrastructure, poor accessibility, and insufficient governmental investment in environmental monitoring and research. Consequently, capturing representative rainfall characteristics required for accurate hydrological modelling becomes challenging. In response to these constraints, remote sensing using satellite-based rainfall products have emerged as a viable alternative, offering broad spatial coverage and high temporal resolution that help address data availability gaps [9]. Satellite-based precipitation products offer globally consistent and spatially homogeneous coverage, providing valuable information for hydrological modelling, particularly in ungauged and data-scarce watersheds [10]. As a result, they are increasingly employed in hydrological modelling, flood forecasting, and disaster risk management.

Reliable rainfall information is fundamental to climate analysis, agricultural planning, flood forecasting, and water resources management. Nevertheless, previous studies indicate that pronounced temporal and spatial variability in precipitation constitutes a major source of uncertainty in land-surface and hydrological simulations, significantly affecting model performance and outputs [11]. Consequently, enhancing the accuracy of quantitative precipitation estimates remains imperative for effective flood risk management and the sustainable planning and management of water resources [12].

Climate prediction is particularly useful for operators in weather-sensitive sectors such as agriculture, aviation, construction, water resources, health, trade, and tourism, individuals, and other stakeholders [13]. However, variability in rainfall patterns is widely recognized as a significant threat to socio-economic development, as it contributes to recurrent drought and flood episodes that disrupt agricultural productivity, water availability, and infrastructure stability [14]. Thus, representative precipitation information is vital for making informed decisions [12], where the economy depends heavily on rainfall.

Jalingo Metropolis, located in Taraba State in northeastern Nigeria, exemplifies a rapidly developing urban environment influenced by pronounced seasonal rainfall variability and increasing climatic fluctuations. Accurate and reliable precipitation information is vital for effective infrastructure planning, flood risk management, and the sustenance of predominantly agrarian livelihoods within the region. However, the availability of continuous, high-quality ground-based rainfall data in Jalingo is limited by sparse gauge networks. Although satellite-based precipitation products provide an alternative source of rainfall information with broad spatial and temporal coverage, their reliability under local climatic conditions remains uncertain. To date, the performance of satellite-derived rainfall estimates over Jalingo has not been comprehensively evaluated using in situ rain gauge observations. In the absence of proper validation, uncritical reliance on satellite precipitation data may result in misleading interpretations and suboptimal decision-making. This study therefore seeks to address this gap by undertaking an evaluation of satellite precipitation estimates for Jalingo using gauge data, with a view to assessing their level of agreement and suitability for local climate and hydrological applications. This work will assist researchers, hydrologists, meteorologists, and policy makers in selecting appropriate rainfall datasets for climate studies, agricultural planning, and flood risk management, and also provide a scientific basis for integrating satellite and ground-based rainfall data in data-scarce regions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing study area (Source: Authour)

Jalingo is the capital city of Taraba State, situated in Northeastern Nigeria. Geographically, the metropolis lies between latitudes $8^{\circ}47'$ and $9^{\circ}01'$ N and longitudes $11^{\circ}09'$ and $11^{\circ}30'$ E. The area falls within the Northern Guinea Savanna ecological zone, which is characterized by grasses interspersed with tall trees and shrubs. Hydrologically, Jalingo metropolis is drained by two major rivers, Mayogwoi and Lamurde, which discharge into the Benue River system at Lau village. The area experiences a distinct wet and dry season, with rainfall largely influenced by the West African Monsoon system. The wet season typically spans from April to October, while the dry season extends from November to March. The dry season is marked by the dominance of the northeast trade winds, commonly referred to as the harmattan, which are generally dry and dusty. Jalingo receives an average annual rainfall of approximately 1,200 mm and has a mean annual temperature of about 29°C . Relative humidity values range from about 60–70 % during the wet season to approximately 35–45 % in the dry season [1].

2.2 Data Collection

Ground-based rainfall observations were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMET) for Jalingo station and used as the reference dataset. The NiMET rainfall records cover the period 2002–2024, spanning 23 years. The dataset consists of quality-controlled gauge measurements representing point-scale rainfall at Jalingo. The gauge data were aggregated to monthly and annual rainfall totals for consistency with the satellite-based datasets.

Satellite-Based Rainfall Products

Satellite-based rainfall estimates corresponding to the location of Jalingo were obtained from TAMSAT (Tropical Applications of Meteorology using SATellite and ground-based observations), CHIRPS (Climate Hazards Group InfraRed Precipitation with Station), PERSIANN (Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks), PERSIANN-PDIR-NOW, and PERSIANN-CCS for the same 23-year period (2002–2024). These datasets were selected due to their extensive application in rainfall monitoring over Africa and their diverse precipitation retrieval methodologies. To ensure comparability, satellite rainfall estimates were temporally aggregated to monthly and annual totals. Since the analysis was conducted at a single point location, the satellite grid cell closest to the NiMET station in Jalingo was selected using the nearest-neighbour approach. This point-to-pixel matching method minimizes spatial mismatch between gauge and satellite rainfall estimates.

2.3 Statistical Metrics

Total rainfall climatology (TRC): Rainfall climatology represents the long-term average of precipitation at a location, typically computed over a 20–30 year period, and provides a baseline for assessing normal conditions and variability relative to observed or modeled values. It is widely used in meteorological and hydrological studies to understand spatial

and temporal rainfall patterns and to detect anomalies or trends [15]. The total rainfall climatology of the various precipitation datasets were computed using an arithmetic mean over a 23 years period (2002–2024).

$$TRC (\bar{X}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N X_i \quad (1)$$

Where:

X_i = Total rainfall for a given period in year X_i

N = Number of years in the climatological record (i.e. 23 years)

Mean Bias Error (MBE): MBE quantifies the systematic tendency of a satellite product to overestimate or underestimate gauge rainfall. It is essential for identifying consistent bias in long-term datasets.

$$MBE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - G_i) \quad (2)$$

Where:

S_i : Satellite precipitation

G_i : Gauge (NiMET) precipitation

n: Number of paired observations

Relative Mean Bias Error (RMBE): RMBE expresses bias as a percentage of observed rainfall, allowing comparison across stations and climatic zones with different rainfall magnitudes.

$$RMBE(\%) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - G_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n G_i} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - G_i)^2} \quad (4)$$

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \bar{S})(G_i - \bar{G})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (S_i - \bar{S})^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (G_i - \bar{G})^2}} \quad (5)$$

Coefficient of Determination (R^2) = r^2 . Coefficient of Determination indicates the proportion of variance in gauge rainfall explained by satellite estimates, reflecting predictive consistency.

Where r = Pearson correlation coefficient

Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE): The KGE is made up of three variables: r , the correlation coefficient; β , the biases; and α , the variability between the two evaluated variables. KGE provides a comprehensive performance measure by jointly considering correlation, bias, and variability, making it ideal for long-term climatological evaluation.

$$KGE = 1 - \sqrt{(r - 1)^2(\beta - 1)^2(\gamma - 1)^2} \quad (6)$$

Where

r = Pearson correlation coefficient

$$\beta = \frac{S}{G} \text{ Bias ratio}$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{CV_S}{CV_G} \text{ Variability ratio}$$

$$CV_S = \frac{\sigma_S}{S}$$

$$CV_G = \frac{\sigma_G}{G}$$

σ_S , σ_G = Standard deviations

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Dat0a Analysis

Both satellite and gauge datasets were processed to ensure temporal consistency. Monthly and seasonal rainfall totals were computed. Statistical metrics including correlation coefficient (r), root mean square error (RMSE) and mean bias error (MBE) were used to evaluate the performance of satellite precipitation estimates relative to ground observations. These metrics are widely applied in satellite rainfall validation studies [16], [17].

3.2 Total Rainfall Climatology

Table 1 shows the total yearly rainfall data for the various datasets

Table 1: Total Yearly Rainfall for Various Datasets (2002-2024)

Year	CHIRPS (mm)	PERSIANN (mm)	PERSIANN CCS (mm)	PERSIANN- PDIR-NOW (mm)	TAMSAT (mm)	NiMET (mm)
2002	1207.1	2165.9	1790	664	1264.4	1260.9
2003	1298.6	2146.9	1775	647	1297.6	1295.1
2004	1219.6	2283.2	2061	734	1205	1202.6
2005	1161.3	1930.7	2516	639	1188.4	1183.7
2006	1305.5	2573.9	2613	1143	1139.8	1134.7
2007	1167.5	2219.1	2466	608	1199.5	1193.9
2008	1361.2	2309.8	2700	1153	1232.7	1225.5
2009	1262	2461.7	1890	822	1231.3	1227.1
2010	1201.6	1995.3	2289	660	1148.1	1142.9
2011	1207.1	2315.9	2289	1072	1148.1	1236.8
2012	1384.5	2210.2	2510	747	1267.2	1263.5
2013	1062.5	1901.1	2122	939	1174.3	1169.8
2014	1173.3	2087.4	2128	745	1233.6	1232.8
2015	1089	2159.8	1587	915	1153	1149.1
2016	1217.3	1922.4	2021	691	1288.4	1283
2017	1063.3	1999.3	1925	726	1088.9	1302.2
2018	1197	2096.7	2190	709	1197.7	1634.9
2019	1157.4	2575	2360	955	1191	2531.2
2020	1117.7	1928.5	1904	578	1183.8	1756.2
2021	1184.2	1674.1	2442	779	1229	2314.6
2022	1132	1673.8	2129	616	1223.3	1776.7
2023	1082.2	1691.4	2361	795	1164.9	1418
2024	1106.4	1575.8	1527	646	1176.6	1121
Mean (TRC)	1189.5	2082.5	2184.9	781.9	1201.2	1393.7

NiMET gauge observations indicate substantial interannual variability in rainfall over Jalingo between 2002 and 2024, with annual totals ranging from about 1,120 mm (2024)

to over 2,530 mm (2019). This variability is characteristic of the Sudano–Guinea savannah climate, where rainfall is controlled by the strength and latitudinal position of the West African Monsoon and associated mesoscale convective systems [18]. The long-term mean annual rainfall from NiMET is approximately 1,394 mm, which is consistent with climatological estimates reported for northeastern Nigeria [19]. NiMET data serve as the benchmark for assessing the predictive performance of satellite-based rainfall products.

CHIRPS reproduces the long-term rainfall climatology of Jalingo reasonably well, although with a slight underestimation of the NiMET mean. Despite this bias, CHIRPS captures the variability of the climatological distribution, making it suitable for climatological applications. This behavior is consistent with findings across West Africa, where CHIRPS is reported to preserve long-term rainfall means and interannual variability due to its incorporation of station data during bias correction [20], [21]. Studies across Nigeria and Ghana show that CHIRPS typically underestimates total rainfall by less than 10% while maintaining high correlation with observed climatology [21].

TAMSAT estimates produce a climatological mean close to NiMET values, though slightly lower. Its performance indicates strong skill in capturing seasonal rainfall structure, but with modest underestimation of total accumulation during wet years. This outcome aligns with recent West African studies indicating that TAMSAT performs well in seasonal climatology and rainfall timing, but often underestimates long-term means because the Cold Cloud Duration (CCD) approach is less sensitive to rainfall intensity [20], [22].

PERSIANN substantially overestimates the rainfall climatology of Jalingo, yielding a long-term mean far exceeding NiMET observations. This overestimation distorts the climatological baseline and reduces its suitability for climate assessment. According to Karbalaei et al [23], this behavior reflects known challenges of PERSIANN, where reliance on infrared cloud-top temperatures causes systematic overestimation of rainfall from cold but weakly precipitating clouds. Similar overestimation of climatological means has been reported in literature, especially in convective regimes [21].

PERSIANN-CCS produces the largest positive deviation from the observed climatology, severely overestimating total rainfall. This suggests poor representation of long-term rainfall conditions in the study area. Recent studies indicate that PERSIANN-CCS tends to systematically inflate rainfall climatology in monsoon-dominated regions due to misclassification of cloud clusters associated with mesoscale convective systems (Lin et al., 2023). Over West Africa, its climatological bias has been shown to exceed 30–50% in some basins [20].

PERSIANN-PDIR NOW significantly underestimates the rainfall climatology, producing a long-term mean well below NiMET observations. This indicates a failure to capture accumulated rainfall adequately. This behavior is typical of near-real-time satellite products without gauge calibration, which tend to miss prolonged rainfall events and underestimate seasonal totals [19], [22].

These results reinforce findings from recent West African studies that gauge-corrected products are best suited for climatological rainfall assessment, while purely satellite-based or near-real-time datasets require substantial bias correction [19], [22].

3.3 Comparison of Satellite Precipitation Datasets with NiMET

Figures 2a-e show the results of total rainfall estimates of the various satellite-based datasets and NiMET gauge station

Figure 2a: CHIRPS and NiMET Total Yearly Rainfall

Figure 2b: PERSIANN and NiMET Total Yearly Rainfall

Figure 2a shows that CHIRPS demonstrates strong agreement with NiMET annual rainfall totals for most part of the study period, with relatively small deviations from NiMET values. Variations in both rainfall amounts differ by less than 5 %, except for

year 2018-2023, where estimates of CHIRPS rainfall amount differ by over 20 % as against NiMET gauge data. . Although CHIRPS slightly underestimates rainfall in some wetter years; it consistently captures the interannual variability and long-term rainfall pattern. This strong performance reflects the design of CHIRPS, which combines infrared satellite estimates with gauge observations to reduce bias, particularly over Africa [24]. Similar results have been reported in Nigeria and other West African countries, where CHIRPS was found to outperform purely satellite-based products in reproducing annual rainfall totals [21].

Figures 2b, 2c and 2d shows the comparison of PERSIANN, PERSIANN CCS, and PERSIANN PDIR NOW against NiMET gauge data

Figure 2c: PERSIANN CCS and NiMET Total Yearly Rainfall

Figure 2d: PERSIANN PDIR NOW and NiMET Total Yearly Rainfall

Results show that the PERSIANN family consistently overestimates annual rainfall compared with NiMET across nearly all years. PERSIANN-CCS shows the largest deviation from NiMET observations, with annual rainfall totals that are consistently and

substantially higher than observed values. In many years (e.g., 2005, 2006, 2008, and 2023), PERSIANN-CCS produces rainfall totals exceeding 2,000 mm when NiMET observations are much lower. This systematic positive bias has been widely reported in tropical and monsoon-dominated regions. The neural-network algorithm used by PERSIANN heavily relies on infrared cloud-top temperatures, which can lead to exaggerated rainfall estimates when cold but weakly precipitating clouds are present [23], [25]. Recent evaluations over West Africa indicate that PERSIANN-CCS tends to overestimate rainfall in regions dominated by mesoscale convective systems due to misclassification of cloud clusters [23]. This leads to inflated annual totals and poor representation of observed rainfall climatology [20]. On the other hand, PERSIANN-PDIR NOW exhibits systematic underestimation of annual rainfall relative to NiMET throughout the study period. In almost all years, its rainfall totals are substantially lower than observed values, indicating difficulty in capturing accumulated rainfall. This underestimation reflects the limitations of near-real-time satellite products that lack gauge adjustment. Such products often miss prolonged rainfall events and underestimate rainfall magnitude, especially in monsoon-influenced climates [19], [22].

The comparison of TAMSAT estimates against NiMET data is presented in Figure 2e. TAMSAT also shows reasonable agreement ($< 1\%$ variation) with NiMET for most part of the period under study. This behaviour has been reported in literatures, showing that TAMSAT, which relies on cold cloud duration techniques, performs well in detecting rainfall occurrence and seasonal timing but often underestimates rainfall magnitude during intense convective events [20], [26].

Figure 2e: TAMSAT Total Yearly Rainfall Estimate vs NiMET

Table 2 shows the average monthly precipitation for the various datasets; while Table 3 shows performance statistics of the five satellite rainfall datasets (CHIRPS, PERSIANN, PERSIANN-CCS, PERSIANN-PDIR, and TAMSAT) evaluated against the observed NiMET gauge data for Jalingo (2002–2024) using standard performance metrics. These

metrics include Mean Bias Error (MBE), Relative Mean Bias Error (rMBE), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r), and Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE).

Table 2: Average Monthly Precipitation for Various Datasets (2002-2024)

Month	CHIRPS (mm)	PERSI ANN (mm)	PERSIAN CCS (mm)	PERSIAN-PDIR NOW (mm)	TAMSAT (mm)	NiMET (mm)
Jan	0.4	1.1	15.1	0.7	0.7	0.4
Feb	1.1	5.9	31.5	1.8	1.8	1.8
March	13.6	25.6	90.0	5.1	5.1	14.6
April	63.0	191.7	331.8	53.1	53.1	89.1
May	178.5	342.8	398.4	104.1	104.1	164.5
June	178.1	330.5	255.5	126.1	126.1	206.8
July	222.6	321.0	211.6	148.4	148.4	250.4
Aug	262.8	286.5	169.6	154.7	154.7	297.7
Sept	235.9	340.9	285.4	132.1	132.1	260.6
Oct	94.0	222.1	314.9	52.9	52.9	99.5
Nov	2.0	13.6	56.6	2.5	2.5	8.4
Dec	0.3	1.0	7.0	0.3	0.3	0.0

Table 3: Performance Statistics for Satellite Rainfall Products vs. NiMET Gauge Data

Dataset	MBE (mm)	rMBE	RMSE (mm)	Pearson r	KGE
TAMSAT	-51.00	-0.44	71.37	0.99	0.56
CHIRPS	-11.79	-0.10	19.09	0.99	0.9
PERSIANN	57.41	0.49	83.85	0.92	0.49
PERSIANN-PDIR	-51.00	-0.44	71.37	0.99	0.56
PERSIANN-CCS	64.47	0.56	125.85	0.61	0.29

Bias reflects whether a satellite dataset consistently over- or under-estimates rainfall compared to gauge observations. CHIRPS shows the lowest bias (MBE ≈ -11.79 mm; rMBE ≈ -0.10), indicating strong agreement with the NiMET station observations. In

contrast, PERSIANN and PERSIANN-CCS show notable overestimation, while TAMSAT and PERSIANN-PDIR exhibit significant underestimation. The presence of systematic bias in satellite rainfall estimates is consistent with findings from several regional evaluations. For example, a study over multiple West African basins noted that many products tend to underestimate or overestimate precipitation depending on climatic zone and dataset characteristics, and that PERSIANN often yields higher bias relative to other products in similar validation exercises [20].

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) quantifies the overall magnitude of errors, with lower values indicating closer agreement with gauge observations. In this study, CHIRPS has the lowest RMSE (≈ 19.09 mm), indicating better precision in capturing the magnitude of rainfall events. PERSIANN-CCS has the largest RMSE (≈ 125.85 mm), reflecting substantial deviation from observed values. These results are in agreement with the findings that showed that CHIRPS typically outperforms PERSIANN in capturing both the magnitude and variability of rainfall over monthly to seasonal scales due to its calibration with station data [27].

Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) integrates correlation, bias ratio (β), and variability ratio (γ) into a single measure of performance. In this relationship, values closer to 1.0 indicate better overall skill. CHIRPS achieved the highest KGE (~ 0.90), highlighting its balanced reliability across multiple error dimensions. TAMSAT and PERSIANN-PDIR exhibit moderate KGE values (~ 0.56), while PERSIANN and particularly PERSIANN-CCS fall short (~ 0.49 and ~ 0.29 respectively), reflecting poor overall performance.

Use of KGE in satellite rainfall validation has become common because it addresses the limitations of isolated metrics like RMSE or correlation alone. According to Knoben (2019), the KGE values range from $-\infty$ to 1, where a value of 1 indicates a perfect fit to the in situ data. Studies evaluating gridded rainfall products across West African basins have used KGE with similar interpretations, showing that products like CHIRPS and gauge-corrected datasets often perform better than machine-learning based estimates such as PERSIANN-type products [20].

Evaluations across different Nigerian zones (Sahel, Savannah, Guinea) indicate that CHIRPS and TAMSAT generally outperform PERSIANN-type products in capturing rainfall distribution and seasonality. Similarly, a multi-country study in Ghana and Zambia reported that products integrating gauge data (CHIRPS, TAMSAT) perform more consistently than others, though all products showed varying biases across seasons and rainfall intensities [22].

4. Conclusion

Evaluation of five satellite-based precipitation products against NiMET gauge data over Jalingo shows that all satellite products were able to reproduce the general unimodal rainfall regime of Jalingo, but differs in their ability to accurately estimate rainfall magnitude and variability. Among the evaluated products, CHIRPS exhibited the best overall performance relative to NiMET observations, as indicated by its very low RMSE, minimal bias (MBE and rMBE close to zero), strong Pearson correlation coefficient, and the highest Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE). These results demonstrate that CHIRPS most effectively captures both the temporal variability and magnitude of rainfall in Jalingo, making it the most reliable dataset for hydrological modeling, climate variability studies, and water resources assessment in the region. TAMSAT and PERSIANN-PDIR NOW also showed strong correlations with gauge observations, but exhibited moderate negative biases, suggesting a tendency to underestimate rainfall amounts.

In contrast, PERSIANN and PERSIANN-CCS consistently overestimated rainfall, particularly during the core rainy season, resulting in higher RMSE values and lower KGE scores. The relatively weak correlation observed for PERSIANN-CCS further limits its applicability for climate and hydrological studies in Jalingo. Overall, the findings emphasize the necessity of local validation of satellite precipitation products, as their performance varies considerably across datasets and climatic settings.

References

1. Umeh, P. P., Nkwocha, K. F., & Iheukwumere, S. O. (2019). Geographical analysis of household waste generation and disposal in Taraba State, Northeast Nigeria. *International Journal of Geography and Geology*, **8**(2), 58–68.
2. Ayehu, G. T., Tadesse, T., Gessesse, B., & Dinku, T. (2018). Validation of new satellite rainfall products over the Upper Blue Nile Basin, Ethiopia. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, **11**, 1921–1936.
3. Liu, J., Zhou, Z., Yan, Z., Gong, J., Jia, Y., Xu, C.-Y., & Wang, H. (2019). A new approach to separating the impacts of climate change and multiple human activities on water cycle processes based on a distributed hydrological model. *Journal of Hydrology*, **578**, 124096.
4. Asfaw, A., Simane, B., Hassen, A., & Bantider, A. (2018). Variability and time series trend analysis of rainfall and temperature in north-central Ethiopia: A case study in Woleka sub-basin. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, **19**, 29–41.
5. Taxak, A. K., Murumkar, A., & Arya, D. (2014). Long-term spatial and temporal rainfall trends and homogeneity analysis in Wainganga Basin, Central India. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, **4**, 50–61.
6. Kardhana, H., Rohmat, F. I. W., Adiprayoga, M. F., Nurhami, A., Solehudin, Wijayasar, W., Kurniawati, S., & Mutiawati, R. H. (2025). Integrating ground-based and satellite rainfall data for

- hydrological modeling: A SWAT+ application with sensitivity analysis in the Saguling Watershed, Citarum River Basin. *Results in Engineering*, **27**, 106370.
7. Putra, M., Rosid, M. S., & Handoko, D. (2024). A review of rainfall estimation in Indonesia: Data sources, techniques, and methods. *Signals*, **5**, 542–561.
 8. Rohmat, F. I. W., Harjupa, W., Rohmat, D., & Rohmat, F. I. W. (2023). The impacts of global atmospheric circulations on water supply in selected watersheds in the Indonesian maritime continent using SPI. *Heliyon*, **9**.
 9. de Aguiar, J. T., & Lobo, M. (2020). Reliability and discrepancies of rainfall and temperature from remote sensing and Brazilian ground weather stations. *Remote Sensing Applications: Society and Environment*, **18**, 100301.
 10. Chen, J., Li, Z., Li, L., Wang, J., Qi, W., Xu, C., & Kim, J. (2020). Evaluation of multi-satellite precipitation datasets and their error propagation in hydrological modeling in a monsoon-prone region. *Remote Sensing*, **12**, 3550.
 11. Kaprom, C., Williams, J. A., Mehrotra, R., Ophaphaibun, C., & Sriwongsitanon, N. (2025). A comprehensive evaluation of the accuracy of satellite-based precipitation estimates over Thailand. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*, **59**, 102380.
 12. Wodebo, D. Y., Melesse, A. M., Woldesenbet, K. M., Amdihun, A., Korecha, D., Tedla, H. Z., Corzo, G., & Teshome, A. (2025). Comprehensive performance evaluation of satellite-based and reanalysis rainfall estimate products in Ethiopia for drought, flood, and water resources applications. *Journal of Hydrology: Regional Studies*, **57**, 102150.
 13. Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMET). (2025). *NiMET 2025 news bulletin*. Retrieved January 9, 2026, from <https://nimet.gov.ng/news?id=73>
 14. Sharma, M., & Sharma, S. R. (2025). Impacts of climate variability on hydrological extremes: Droughts and floods in a changing climate. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Management*, **10**(36s), 149–167.
 15. Omay, P. O., Muthama, N. J., Oludhe, C., Kinama, J. M., Artan, G., & Atheru, Z. (2025). Evaluation of satellite-based rainfall estimates over the IGAD region of Eastern Africa. *Meteorology and Atmospheric Physics*, **137**, 22.
 16. Dinku, T., Cousin, R., Maidment, R., Tarnavsky, E., Connor, S., & Peterson, P. (2018). Validation of satellite rainfall estimates over Africa. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, **19**(6), 1065–1084.
 17. Satgé, F., Bonnet, M.-P., Gosset, M., Molina, J., Lima, W., Zolá, R. P., & Timouk, F. (2020). Assessment of satellite rainfall products over complex terrain in West Africa. *Atmospheric Research*, **235**, 104746.
 18. Nicholson, S. E. (2013). The West African Sahel: A review of recent studies on the rainfall regime and its interannual variability. *ISRN Meteorology*, **2013**, 1–32.
 19. Dembélé, M., & Schaeffli, B. (2020). Suitability of gridded precipitation datasets for large-scale hydrological modelling in West Africa. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, **24**, 5379–5401.
 20. Goudiaby, O., Bodian, A., Dezetter, A., Diouf, I., & Ogilvie, A. (2024). Evaluation of gridded rainfall products in West African basins. *Hydrology*, **11**(6), 75.
 21. Poudyal, R., et al. (2024). Evaluation of satellite-based rainfall estimates against rain-gauge observations across agro-climatic zones of Nigeria. *Remote Sensing*, **16**(10), 1755.

22. Bagiliko, J., Stern, D., Ndanguza, D., & Torgbor, F. F. (2025). Validation of satellite and reanalysis rainfall products against rain gauge observations in Ghana and Zambia. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, **156**, 241.
23. Karbalaee, N., Hsu, K., Sorooshian, S., & Braithwaite, D. (2017). Bias adjustment of infrared-based rainfall estimation using passive microwave satellite rainfall data. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, **122**(7), 3859–3876. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JD026037>
24. Funk, C., Peterson, P., Landsfeld, M., Pedreros, D., Verdin, J., Shukla, S., Husak, G., Rowland, J., Harrison, L., & Hoell, A. (2015). The Climate Hazards Infrared Precipitation with Stations (CHIRPS): A new environmental record for monitoring extremes. *Scientific Data*, **2**, 150066. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2015.66>
25. Ashouri, H., Hsu, K.-L., Sorooshian, S., Braithwaite, D., Knapp, K. R., Cecil, L. D., Nelson, B. R., & Prat, O. P. (2015). PERSIANN-CDR: Daily precipitation climate data record from multisatellite observations. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, **96**, 69–83.
26. Maidment, R. I., Grimes, D., Black, E., Tarnavsky, E., Young, M., Greatrex, H., Allan, R. P., Stein, T., Nkonde, E., Senkunda, S., & Alcántara, E. M. U. (2017). A new long-term daily satellite-based rainfall dataset for operational monitoring in Africa. *Scientific Data*, **4**, 170063. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.63>
27. Ogidi, M. A., Oyegoke, S. O., & Akintola, O. A. (2025). Comparative evaluation of satellite-derived rainfall data with ground observations in southwestern Nigeria. *UNIABUJA Journal of Engineering and Technology*, **2**(2), 45–57.